

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF ORAL HYGIENE IN PATIENTS WITH PARTIALLY REMOVABLE DENTURES ON THE PERIODONTIUM

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Abstract

In the clinic, an index assessment of the condition of periodontal tissues makes it possible to quantify the level of oral hygiene, the severity of the pathological process, and the severity of bone destruction. With its help, you can get a general idea of the nature of the disease, plan the scope of treatment interventions, and evaluate the effectiveness of the treatment.

Keywords: oral hygiene, partially removable lamellar dentures, clasp dentures.

Material and methods.

To conduct the study, three groups of patients with partial terminal defects of the dentition were identified, to restore the integrity of which removable dentures with various fixation methods were used. Group 1 included patients with partial absence of teeth, for whose replacement partial removable laminar dentures were chosen.

The 2nd group consisted of patients who, to restore the integrity of the dentition, chose solid clasp dentures with a clasp fixation system.

In the 3rd group, solid clasp dentures with locking fixation were used as removable dentures. In the 1st group of patients, the OHI-S index at the beginning of orthopedic treatment was the highest compared to other groups and amounted to 3.33 ± 0.05 , which indicates a low level of oral hygiene. During the follow-up examination after 6 months, the indicator significantly decreased and amounted to 2.79 ± 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). The increase in hygiene level is explained by motivation and professional hygiene. However, another 6 months after the application of the prostheses, the index increased slightly - to 2.97 ± 0.04 . At the same time, it should be noted that the OHI-S index scores after 12 months were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than those at the time of seeking dental orthopedic care. The gingival GI index corresponded to a mild degree of inflammation and averaged 0.99 ± 0.02 . After therapeutic and periodontological preparation of patients for prosthetics, replacement of dentition defects with partial removable dentures, the gingival index was significantly lower than the initial values and amounted to 0.82 ± 0.02 ($p < 0.05$). 12 months after the application of the prostheses, the GI index significantly increased to 0.88 ± 0.02 ($p < 0.05$), but did not reach the initial values. We explain this by patients getting used to dentures and reducing their demands on oral hygiene.

Results.

The complex periodontal index in patients of group 1, which was 4.46 ± 0.04 at the beginning of treatment, was interpreted as a severe degree of the disease,

which is explained by age and a large number of lost teeth. However, during treatment, the CPI decreased slightly and after 6 and 12 months was 4.24 ± 0.05 and 4.42 ± 0.05 , respectively. In the 2nd group of patients, whose replacement prostheses were solid clasp dentures with clasp fixation, the OHI-S index values at the beginning of treatment were significantly lower than the indicators of the 1st group - 2.78 ± 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). 6 months after the application of the prostheses, the index value decreased to 2.41 ± 0.05 and then, after 12 months, increased again to 2.57 ± 0.04 . These changes indicate that patients after oral cavity sanitation have an adequate attitude towards their dental health, but over time they take it for granted and reduce the level of demands on themselves. The value of the GI index in group 2 varied significantly from the baseline after 6 and 12 months within 0.86 ± 0.02 , 0.72 ± 0.01 and 0.80 ± 0.02 , respectively ($p < 0.05$), which indicates a slight positive effect of clasp

dentures with clasp fixation due to the distribution of part of the chewing load on the supporting teeth. According to the index assessment, the CPI in group 2 significantly decreased from 3.89 ± 0.04 at the beginning of treatment to 3.23 ± 0.09 after 6 months ($p < 0.05$), and after 12 months of using solid clasp with prostheses increased to 3.56 ± 0.07 , but still remained below the original level. An index assessment of the level of hygiene and condition of periodontal tissues when replacing dentition defects with clasp dentures with locking fixation in the 3rd group presented the best indicators. Thus, the OHI-S index had the lowest value after 6 months (1.59 ± 0.06) and was significantly lower than the corresponding values at the beginning of treatment and after 12 months (2.52 ± 0.05 and 1.85 ± 0.06 ; $p < 0.05$). The GI index values also showed positive changes. 6 months after the application of the combined structures, patients noted a decrease in the severity of inflammation in the periodontal tissues, but after another 6 months the GI index increased insignificantly (0.62 ± 0.02 and 0.71 ± 0.02 , respectively; $p < 0.05$). Patients of the 3rd group revealed the positive possibilities

of clasp dentures with fixation on attachments for maintaining dental status at a relatively high level. Thus, when examining patients, it was at the level of 3.75 ± 0.05 and significantly decreased to 2.99 ± 0.09 after 6 months, but increased slightly after 12 months (3.27 ± 0.07 ; $p < 0.05$) after applying prostheses. A comparison of the results of clinical observations, index assessment of the level of oral hygiene and the condition of periodontal tissues of supporting teeth showed that the effectiveness of treatment depends on the design features of the removable dentures and supporting elements used.

Conclusion.

Our experimental and clinical studies confirm the clinical effectiveness, high functional and aesthetic per-

formance of clasp dentures with fixation on attachments, subject to strict adherence to the indications for their use and manufacturing methods.

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